

R.V. COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING, BENGALURU - 560 059
(Autonomous Institution Affiliated to VTU, Belagavi, Karnataka)

PROJECT REPORT

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Isolation, extraction and characterization of essential oils from *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Bacopa monnieri* leaves and *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers

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ABSTRACT

Denaturation of components present in essential oils obtained via Steam Distillation process, on account of exposure to high temperatures for long periods of time (10 days), leads to the loss of their pharmacological properties. Furthermore, upon obtaining low yields via the aforementioned extraction process, most of the oils available in the market have been adulterated. Therefore in the present work, solvent extraction of essential oils was conducted using a Soxhlet extractor, thus resulting in a higher yield and lesser duration of time taken for extraction process.

Extraction of essential oils present in the leaves of *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis* and *Bacopa monnieri*, and flowers of *Hibiscus rosasinensis* was done by using a combination of Soxhlet extraction, Simple distillation and Centrifugation. Phytochemical tests were conducted to detect the presence of Terpenoids, Diterpenes, Triterpenoids, Glycosides, Cardiac Glycosides, Saponins, Tannins, Phenolic compounds, Steroids, Polyesterols, Proteins, Carbohydrates, Anthraquinones, Flavonoids and Alkaloids in the supernatant obtained upon downstream processing of the essential oils. The essential oils were subjected to Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) to successfully isolate certain chemical constituents present within. Characterization of the extracted essential oils was carried out by Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopy.

The downstream processing involved in extraction of essential oils, gave us a yield of 6.25%, 5.47%, 8.45% and 4.05% for *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Bacopa monnieri* and *Hibiscus rosasinensis* oils, respectively. On an average, we received positive results indicating the presence of Cardiac Glycosides, Tannins and Phenolic compounds, when Phytochemical tests were performed on the supernatant obtained upon concentration of the essential oils. FT-IR analyses of the obtained oils were compared to the results provided by the literature and stark differences were documented.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Bacopa M.: Bacopa monnieri

CCE: Counter Current Extraction

DSP: Down Stream Processing.

DNA: Deoxy ribo nucleic acid.

FeCl₃: Ferric chloride

FT-IR: Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy

HPLC: High Performance Liquid Chromatography

H₂SO₄: Sulphuric Acid

Hibiscus R.: Hibiscus Rosa-senensis

Laurus N.: Laurus nobilis

M.S: Mass Spectrometry

MPLC: Medium Pressure Liquid Chromatography

Mentha A.: Mentha arvensis

NMR: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy

rpm: rotations per minute

SFE: Supercritical Fluid Extraction

SEC: Size Exclusion Chromatography

TLC: Thin Layer Chromatography

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Essential oils are secondary metabolites that plants produce to protect themselves from infections, damage, predators and weather variations. These secondary metabolites are chemical stress management tools that are known to have pharmacological properties like antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anti-tumoral which helps in protecting DNA and cell membrane from damages, damages and improves in immune stimulation, vasodilation, mood elevation, oxygenation of tissues, muscle relaxation and balancing of brain chemistry. ^[1]

1.1 A BRIEF HISTORY OF ESSENTIAL OILS

Our knowledge of essential oil usage dates back to the Pre-historic era where certain herbs, roots and juices were extracted from plants for the treatment of wounds and skin conditions. Early references to essential oils considered the perfumes made by the Egyptians in 300 BC, which had a variety of applications in body massages, reflexology, cosmetology, aromatherapy and pharmacy. They used a method known as Enfleurage for extraction of aromatic compounds from plants. The Egyptian priests used a blend of essential oils known as Kyphi to cleanse the body and bring restful sleep, which was documented by Manetho in a text titled, "Preparation of Kyphi recipes". ^[2]

After Egyptians, the Chinese were experts in using the essential oils. Huyang Ti in 2700 BC, authored a book entitled "Yellow Emperors Classic of Internal Medicine", which had documented most of the ancient Chinese herbal traditions that we know of today. From the Vedas we found that the 2000 BC dawned the era of Ayurvedic Medicine. The Vedas is one of the earliest books which explain the first written formulae for preparation of blends of essential oils. The Rig Veda covers medicinal properties of over 700 substances. The Ayurvedic medicine system is one of the oldest practiced by mankind.

In the Biblical times, the recipe for "Moses Holy Anointing Oil" was provided in the Journal, Exodus (Vol. 30, pp 23-24) which mentions the use of Myrrh, Cassia, Cinnamon, Calamus, Frankincense, Galbanum and Onycha essential oils.

In 78 AD, a Greek surgeon, Discorides authored a book entitled “Materia Medica Vol.5”, which described medicinal properties of over 600 plants present in the Mediterranean region. This book played an important role in development of medicine for the next 1000 years. Known as the “Father of Holistic Medicine”, Hippocrates was known to have worked on 200 different herbs during his lifetime. Dioscorides had authored a paper entitled, “Concerning Odours” which described the physical and emotional effects of the use of fragrances. [2]

Further sophisticated use of blends and fragrances prepared by the Egyptians and the Greeks were practiced for more than a decade before the arrival of the Romans. Galen (131-200 AD), a Greek pharmacist wrote over 20 books on “Plant and Animal Drug Formulations”. Galenic Pharmacy refers to his collection of works.

In 800 AD, an Arab scientist, Al Khindi authored a book entitled “Chemistry of Perfumes and Distillation”, which was then followed by Avicenna (980-1037 AD), who authored “Canon of Medicine” (a standard text book used till mid 16th century). Avicenna was also recognized to have invented the Steam Distillation process for production of perfumes.

The middle ages (500-1300 AD), marked the search for the Elixir of Life. The Alchemists made many discoveries during this age; one of which being the Quintessence element (5th element). Alchemists believed in the 4 basic elements that govern everything in nature- Air, Fire, Water and Earth. Upon distillation, they discovered the oil layer, which was formed over the water and termed it as Quintessential layer. This marked the onset of Essential oil preparation. [2]

By 15th century, during the Renaissance, 60-70 essential oils became popular. In 16th century the essential oils became commonly available at the Apothecary shops. In the 1596, a book entitled “The Grete Herball”, written by Heironymus Braunsweig explained the production of 25 essential oils.

By the 17th and 18th century, essential oils became very common and were often used for their medicinal properties. 19th century marked the separation of production of perfumery from Apothecary. A place called Grasse in southern France became the major centre for cultivation and extraction of Perfumes; it later became the Perfume capital of the country.

The 20th century became popular for analyses of plants and their products. Rene Gatteforse, a French Perfumer and chemist coined the term “Aromatherapie” in 1928. A scientist Dr. Jean Valnet had authored “Practice of Aromatherapy” in 1954 and a biochemist, Marguerite Maury authored a book entitled “Secrets to Life and Youth” in 1964. [2]

1.2 EXTRACTION OF ESSENTIAL OILS

Techniques for essential oil extraction from medicinal plants include Maceration, Headspace trapping, Sonication, Percolation, Supercritical fluid extraction, Phytonic extraction, Hydrodistillation techniques, Soxhlet extraction, Infusion, Protoplast extraction, Digestion, Solid phase micro extraction, Decoction, Molecular distillation, Counter current extraction, aqueous- alcoholic extraction, etc. However, the present work enumerates the principle behind a few of the aforementioned extraction processes.

1.2.1 Maceration

In Maceration presented in Figure 1.1 plant product, present in a container, takes approximately 3 days to dissolve in a solvent, after which the wet solid is compressed and then subjected to filtration.

Figure 1.1: Maceration process

1.2.2 Digestion

Although digestion is a form of Maceration, it uses a moderate temperature, while Maceration involves the use of high temperatures.

1.2.3 Decoction

Ayurvedic extracts like “quath” or “kawath”, mostly uses Decoction as the process of extraction. In this process, plant material is boiled in a specified volume of water, for a standardized amount of time, before being cooled and subjected to filtration (Figure 1.2). Ratio of the powder to water is fixed. Filtration is done once the volume of the solution decreases to $\frac{1}{4}$ its original volume upon boiling.

Figure 1.2: Decoction Process

1.2.4 Percolation

In the percolation process, a percolator, having an open cone shaped vessel is used. (Figure 1.3) Menstrum is used to moisten solid ingredients, present in the vessel. It is allowed to stand for 4 hours.

Liquid contained within is allowed flow out of the outlet of the percolator. Additional menstrum is added until the percolate measures about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the required volume of the product. Expressed liquid present in the marc is added to the percolate. Finally the mixed liquid is clarified by filtration or by standing, followed by decantation. This process is used to extract active ingredients and fluid extracts.

Figure 1.3: A Percolator

1.2.5 Hot solvent extraction

In hot solvent extraction, a saché containing the finely powdered material is placed in the thimble chamber of the Soxhlet. A suitable solvent is poured in (Figure 1.4) and the apparatus is heated at an appropriate temperature until the solvent vapors are condensed in the condenser. The condensed liquid drips back into the thimble container. This is a small scale process and is often used as a continuous batch process.

Figure 1.4: Solvent Extractor

1.2.6 Aqueous- alcoholic extraction by fermentation

For fermentation to take place, plant powder is soaked in decoction for a certain period of time. Alcohol and other active constituents of the plant material are generated by the fermented product. Ayurveda has adopted this method to extract active chemical components present in medicinal plants.

Wooden vats, porcelain jars and metal vessels are employed for the fermentation process. Examples of such preparations are Karpurasava, Kanakasava etc.

1.2.7 Sonication

Ultrasound of frequency 20 kHz - 2000 kHz is used to cause cavitation in the plant cell, thus causing the required medicinal compounds present in the plant powder to be dissolved upon addition of solvent.

1.2.8 Supercritical fluid extraction

In Supercritical liquid extraction (SFE) technique the efficiency of the extraction of medicinal compounds increases due to the use of solvents at critical properties (Temp and pressure). In most the SFE liquid Carbon dioxide is used as a solvent due to its capacity to dissolve the compounds at liquid form. SFE allows for extraction of constituents at lower temperatures, thus avoiding degradation of compounds due to heat. It is a very environmentally friendly procedure as there isn't any residual solvent.

1.2.9 Qualitative analysis of essential oils

After the extraction of essential oils, the qualitative analysis of the essential oils is done using Physical tests, Chemical tests and Instrumental techniques. This paper elaborates a few of the aforementioned quality analysis tests.

1.2.9.1 Physical tests

Physical tests for the quality assessments of essential oils includes the determination of Optical rotation, Moisture content, Residue on evaporation , Specific gravity, Refractive index, Freezing and Solubility in dilute alcohol of essential oils.

Moisture content of essential oils is determined by Gas chromatography, spectroscopic and electrometric methods. Desiccating agents such as anhydrous Sodium Sulphate are

used for drying of the sample. To determine the moisture content, 1 ml of carbon disulphide added to 0.5 ml of essential oil, formation of a clear solution indicates that there is no moisture content.

Specific Gravity is determined using a pycnometer. Specific gravity is the weight of a given volume of oil at a specified temperature, when compared to the weight of an equal volume of water, at the same temperature.

Refractive index is the ratio of sine of angle of incidence to the sine of angle of refraction of the beam of light passing from air to the oil.

1.2.9.2 Chemical tests

Chemical tests involve determination of phenol content, ester value, aldehydes, carbonyl value and acid value.

Acid value of essential oils refers to the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the free acids present in 1g of the oil.

The number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide that is equivalent to the amount of hydroxylamine required to oxidize the carbonyl compounds present in 1 g of the oil is the *carbonyl value* of essential oils.

The number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the acids liberated by the hydrolysis of 1 g of the acetylated oil is the *ester value* of essential oils.

1.2.9.3 Instrumental techniques

Most of the instrumental techniques include spectroscopic techniques and chromatographic techniques.

The Chromatographic techniques include Gas Chromatography (GC), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), High Pressure Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Supercritical Fluid chromatography (SFC), Mass Spectrometry (MS) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrometry (NMR).

HPLC, SEC, MPLC, SFC are used for pre-fractionation of complex mixtures of essential oils before conducting a gas chromatographic analysis.

Gas Chromatography is one of the most advanced techniques used for the separation of essential oils constituents. This has a wide range of column packaging materials and detectors. It uses fused silica capillary columns where separation, identification and quantification of numerous constituents in essential oils occur.

This technique is based on separation of volatile compounds of a liquid or a gas mixture which is volatilized in a column packed with a thin film support. Nitrogen or helium gas is commonly used as the mobile phase. Due to the difference in partition coefficients of the components present in the sample, segregation takes place.

1.3 LITERATURE SURVEY

According to a 2009 census, Kumar S. ^[3] comments that there are 390,800 species of plants in the world. Moerman reported that 625 species of these plants have been utilized as food, while 2,564 species are used as drugs. Unfortunately, there are 18,000 types of plants, whose utility properties are unknown.

The terms "essential oil", "volatile oil" and "etheric oil" refer to a liquid contained within specialized cells of plant, which are soluble in organic solvents such as alcohol, fats, alcohol and insoluble in water. Samfira S. and Rodino N.S ^[4] specify that essential oils often occur in a liquid form. However they are sometimes solid or semi-solid oils depending on the room temperature and the temperature in which they are stored.

The aroma of an essential oil is due to the presence of volatile components present in flowers, fruits, seeds and bark of trees. These are complex mixtures of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, Terpenoids, Diterpenes, Triterpenoids, Glycosides, Cardiac glycosides, Saponins, Tannins, Phenolic compounds, Steroids, Polyesterols, Proteins, Carbohydrates, Anthraquinones, Flavonoids and Alkaloids. Extraction of essential oils is an expensive process, due to the large amount of raw material required for a yield of 5-10%. ^[4]

As the yield is low, the perfume industry often makes use of synthetic oils, thus resulting in essential oils with a very low therapeutic grade. Essential oils contain hundreds of chemical compounds that collectively result in providing it with properties such as antiseptic, antibacterial, immune-stimulatory, decongestant, etc. ^[4] For example, sage oil

contains 250 different molecules (75% are esters and 15% monoterpenes). If any biostructure is isolated from the essential oil, it results in its drastic modifications.

The extraction procedure used drastically impacts the quality of essential oil, by modifying the extraction efficiency and retention of volatile compounds. M. Elmastas, I. Gulçin O, Isldak, O. I. Kufrevioglu, K. Ibaoglu and H. Y. Aboul-Enein have conducted a detailed study on new technologies that are developed in order to minimize the loss of volatile compounds and to improve extraction efficiency and reduce the process time. ^[5]

Atanda O.O, Akpan I and Oluwafemi F, ^[6] have mentioned that the classical procedures followed for extraction of essential oil have many drawbacks. Steam distillation procedure separates only volatile compounds, which get denatured most of the time due to high exposure to elevated temperatures. On the other hand, extraction with organic solvents results in the solvent being retained in the essential oil, thus risking one's health. ^[6] They are insufficiently selective, so there are chances of contaminants being dissolved along with the active compounds.

Ranny N ^[7] mentions that characterization of essential oils is done by physicochemical properties' determination, i.e: boiling point, optical rotation, solubility, refractive index, and density. These parameters are important in the detection of adulteration of essential oils. Chromatographic techniques such as gas chromatography (GC) equipped with FID (Flame Ionization Detector) or MS (mass spectrometer) are often used to study the qualitative and quantitative composition of essential oil. ^[7]

For the past few years, people have used essential oils and concentrates; their reasons were jotted down by Kumar S. ^[3], which accounted to varying from the use of lime in flavouring drinks to rosewood and cedar wood in perfumery or to juniper berry oil and lemongrass oil for the preservation of food crops, or to even the use of antimicrobial activities of essential oils in pharmaceuticals, in drug engineering.

Uniyal V. ^[8] has documented that according to industrial sources, essential oils of Basil, Citronella, Lemongrass, varieties of mints, Palmarosa, Sandalwood, Geranium, Lavender, Patchouli are widely used in fragrances and flavors formulations. Besides, flavor and fragrance applications, essential oils are also used in 'Aromatherapy'.

Most of the farmers in India are engaged in traditional agriculture, i.e. growing food crops, which provides poor returns. In addition to the regular crops, if involved in growing essential oil bearing crops under diversified farming program, the farmers would get better returns. India is known to be a home to around 1300 species of aromatic plants. However, only about 50 of these plants produce essential oils that are in demand in the market. ^[8]

1.3.1 *Mentha arvensis*

Introduced into India in 1952 from Japan, *Mentha arvensis*, commonly called as Cornmint, consists of shoots, having over ground stems, large leaves, small flowers and underground rhizomes. ^[9]

M. arvensis finds its application as a cooling compound in fruit flavours, confections, oral care products, mint flavours and beverages. It is cultivated all across the world for the production of menthol which has its use in food, pharmaceutical and perfumery industries. ^[10]

Adam P. ^[11] mentions in his thesis that most of the Lamiaceae family members accumulate Terpenes, Diterpenes, Sesquiterpenes, Isoprenes, Tannins, Phenols and other components in the epidermal glands of leaves, stems and reproductive structures. The composition of the essential oil produced by most plants is dependent on the genotype of the plant and on agronomical conditions such as soil quality, harvest time, crop density, plant age, etc. Factors such as amount of pollution and usage of pesticides play a major role in the quality of essential oils produced.

Peppermint oils are stable in room temperature and exhibit variable behavior when subjected to high rate of evaporation. Oils of low boiling components are assumed to evaporate easily. ^[11] Therefore, the extraction unit would be located close to aromatic plantation.

For the past 40 years, Northern India has been the largest producer of Japanese Mint. Other major mint producing countries are China, Brazil, Thailand and Vietnam. A large part of our country's mint oil is exported and it faces a huge competition in trade with China. Sparreboom A, Cox MC, Acharya and Figg WD ^[12] mentioned the mint oil's

processing and trade activities that are set up in several small towns of U.P. (Rampur, Sambhal, Chandausi, Badaun, and Barabanki), where a large number of farmers, traders, distillers and exporters are associated with this activity. The government has invested Rs 350 crores in this industry.

1.3.2 *Laurus nobilis*

Leaves of *L. nobilis* are used as a spice, an insecticide, an antiseptic, and as a treatment for stomach ache. They are also used to treat rheumatism; references to certify the above statement are present in the European folk medicine literature.

It is commonly known as bay laurel and is a Mediterranean evergreen tree, found mostly in areas such as Turkey, Greece, Spain, Italy and France. Laurel leaves are used as flavouring agents in meat, poultry and fish meals, and as an enhancer in pickles, sauces and canned food. It can prolong the storage life of foods due to its antioxidant and/or antimicrobial activities. Bay leaf is also known to have anticonvulsive and anti-epileptic activities. ^[5]

Bay oil content ranges from 1 to 3% on fresh- weight basis. Lawrance B.M documented the chemical composition of Bay oil which includes 1-8 cineole (45-50%), sabinene, eugenol acetate, pinene, linalool, methyl eugenol, phellandrene, terpineol acetate, eugenol and terpenoids. ^[13]

1.3.3 *Bacopa monnieri*

Bacopa monnieri, is a member of the Scrophulariaceae family and is a small, creeping herb with numerous branches, small leaves and light purple flowers. It grows naturally in marshy lands, at elevations from sea level to a maximum altitude of 4,400 feet and can be cultivated upon availability of adequate water. ^[14]

Documented by Mukherjee DG and Dey CD, *Bacopa* is known to help in relaxing pulmonary arteries, aorta, trachea and bronchial tissue. It is known to possess anti-inflammatory activities and anti-cancerous effects. ^[14]

Research on Ayurvedic medicines has shown that *Bacopa* shows cognitive enhancing effects, especially memory and concentration, and also aides in treatment of anxiety,

epilepsy, bronchitis and asthma, irritable bowel syndrome, and gastric ulcers. ^[14] Recent research concentrates on the development of drugs from Bacoside A, an active component in Brahmi oil, for the treatment of Parkinson's disease.

1.3.4 *Hibiscus rosasinensis*

Hibiscus R., also known as "Japa", "Jasum" and "Jaba", is an evergreen shrub of about 1.5-2.4 m, having bright flowers of colours red, white and yellow. Also called as "Keshya" in Ayurvedic medicines, Hibiscus aides in hair growth and are commonly used in shampoos. ^[15]

Hibiscus oil extracted from the leaves and stems is known to contain tarxeryl acetate, β -sitosterol, stigma sterol and cyclopropane derivatives, while the flowers contain flavonoids, niacin, vitamins, cyaniding diglucoside, riboflavin, ascorbic acid and thiamine.

K.N.V. Rao, Geetha K., Alagar Raja M. and David Banji authored a paper entitled "Quality Control study and standardization of *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers and leaves as per WHO guidelines", where in they have described that yellow Hibiscus flowers are rich in cyaniding-3,5-diglucoside, Quercetin-3-diglucoside, 3,7 diglucoside and cyaniding 3-sophoroside-5-glucosede, while the white flowers contain all the aforementioned compounds and kaempferol-3-xylosyl glucoside. ^[16]

Its pharmacological uses include abortifacient effect, barbiturate potentiation, acid phosphate stimulation, β gluconidase activity, alkaline phosphate inhibition, β gluconidase stimulation, analgesic activity, CNS depressant activity, androgenic effect, contragestative agents, anticonvulsive activity, embryotoxic effect, anti-FSH activity, estrogenic effect, anti-estrogenic effect, estrous cycle disruption effect, anti-fertility effect, gonadotropin synthesis inhibition, anti-fungal activity, hypoglycemic effect, anti-gonadotropin effect, hypotensive activity, anti-hypertensive activity, hypothermic activity, anti-implantation effect, inotropic effect positive, anti-inflammatory activity, juvenile hormone activity, anti-ovulatroy effect, plant germination inhibition, anti-pyretic activity, lactate-dehydrogenase-X-inhibtion, anti-spasmodic activity, antispermatogenetic

effect, leuteotopic effect, menstruation induction effect, anti-viral activity, radical scavenging effect, teratogenic effect and toxicity assessment. ^[16]

1.4 EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES

The literature available on extraction of essential oils is primarily based on the Steam distillation process. Although there are advancements made in adopting Soxhlet extraction and Vacuum Distillation, there still exist numerous issues that have to be addressed when it comes to extraction of essential oils. In the literature, detailed account on pharmacological activities of certain chemical constituents such as Bacoside A (present in *Bacopa monnieri* oil) has been enumerated and its role played the treatment of Parkinson's disease can be considered for further research.

1.5 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Denaturation of components present in essential oils obtained via Steam Distillation process, on account of exposure to high temperatures for long periods of time (10 days), leads to the loss of their pharmacological properties. Furthermore, upon obtaining low yields via the aforementioned extraction process, most of the oils available in the market have been adulterated.

Therefore in the present work, solvent extraction of essential oils was conducted using a Soxhlet extractor, thus resulting in a higher yield and lesser duration of time taken for extraction process.

1.6 MOTIVATION

The present work address the issues related to the quality and quantity of essential oils obtained from *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis* and *Bacopa monnieri* leaves, and *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers via the steam distillation process. Upon successful extraction of essential oils, characterization using TLC and FT-IR spectroscopy was necessary to check for the presence of certain chemical constituents mentioned in the marketed oils.

1.7 OBJECTIVES

The main aim of carrying out this project work was to extract essential oils from *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* and *Hibiscus R.*, and characterize using TLC and FT-IR.

The objectives of our project include the following:

1. Extraction of essential oils from *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* and *Hibiscus R.*
2. Phytochemical analysis of supernatant obtained upon extraction of the essential oils.
3. Characterization of the extracted oils from TLC and FT-IR spectroscopy.

1.8 METHOD OF APPROACH

To accomplish the aforementioned objectives, specific approaches were optimized upon deducing their effectiveness and then performed to obtain results.

The first objective was achieved by conducting a set of experiments with various solvents to achieve an optimal yield percentage. The second required specific biochemical tests and reagents preparation techniques for Phytochemical analysis to be performed. The last objective was to characterize essential oils extracted, using TLC and FTIR. Solvents were prepared based on existing concentrations mentioned in research papers and were slightly modified to suit the requirements. The results obtained were in concordance with previous papers detailing the extraction and characterization results for *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M* and *Hibiscus R.* essential oils.

1.9 ORGANISATION OF THE REPORT

The main body of this research paper is preceded by an Abstract, a detailed Table of Contents, List of Abbreviations, List of Tables, Figures and Graphs and an Introduction Liter, covering the Literature survey. This research paper is organized into five chapters, which is followed by the references and annexure.

Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION contains the basic information on essential oils, literature survey and the main objectives of the project.

Chapter 2 THEORY AND CONCEPTS incorporates chemical compounds present in essential oils, their applications, and pharmacological properties.

Chapter 3 METHODS AND MATERIALS illustrates the materials, its sources, and the methods/techniques used for the project.

Chapter 4 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND SETUP gives us a succinct methodology of aforementioned objectives as well as experimental setup.

Chapter 5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION incorporates results, graphical analysis, and chromatograms for the aforementioned objectives.

Chapter 6 CONCLUSION AND SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK presents the conclusion drawn from the results and also scope for future work.

CHAPTER 2

THEORY AND CONCEPTS

The principle behind the formulated hypothesis, adopted TLC and FT-IR Spectroscopy to meet the objectives, which has been discussed with relevant pathways and formulae used to evaluate the results.

2.1 SOXHLET EXTRACTION

The Solvent Extraction method discussed in section 1.9 was adopted for extraction of essential oils due to its advantages over steam distillation.

Due to their higher percentage yield as per the literature survey, Ethanol, Chloroform, Benzene and Petroleum Ether, were used as solvents for essential oil extraction from *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis* and *Bacopa monnieri* leaves, and *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers.

2.2 THEORETICAL CONCEPTS OF THE PLANT SPECIES USED

2.2.1. *Mentha arvensis*

Figure 2.1: Leaves of *Mentha A.*

Table 2.1: Taxonomical Classification of *Mentha arvensis*

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Angiosperms
Subdivision	Eudicots
Clade	Asterids
Order	Lamiales
Family	Lamiaceae
Genus	Mentha
Species	<i>arvensis</i>

Mentha A., as shown in Figure 2.1, belongs to the Lamiaceae family (Table 2.1). The family spans over 236 genera and around 6900-7200 species, amongst which Salvia is the largest genera, having 900 species, followed by Scutellaria genera, having 360 species and Stachys genera, having around 300 species. The plants such as basil, mint, rosemary, sage, oregano, thyme and lavender will falls under this family which are widely used as culinary herbs.

The chemical constituents present in the *Mentha arvensis* oil (shown in Figure 2.2), comprises of Limonene, α - Pinene, 1,8- Cineole, β - Pinene, P- Cymene, 3- Octanol, Menthone, Iso- menthone, Menthyl acetate, Iso- Pulegol, Neo- Menthol, Menthol, Pulegone and Piperitone.

Figure 2.2. Chemical constituents present in *Mentha A.* Oil

Mentha arvensis' extracts have been widely used in Ayurveda to treat one suffering from Gastric issues. Mint extracts are also used in soft drinks, food, cigarettes, cough medicine, and facial creams. They are used as a Topical antibacterial agent, which aides in fighting Streptococci and Lactobacilli.

2.2.2. *Laurus nobilis*

Figure 2.3: Leaves of *Laurus N.*

Table 2.2: Taxonomical Classification of *Laurus nobilis*

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Angiosperms
Clade	Magnoliids
Order	Leurales
Family	Lauraceae
Genus	Laurus
Species	<i>Nobilis</i>

Laurus nobilis, presented in Figure 2.3, are small evergreen trees, belonging to the Lauraceae family (Table 2.2). The plant is of industrial importance and is widely used in foods, drugs and cosmetics. Its antimicrobial and insecticidal activities results in its usage as a food preservative in the food industry. Volatile components of essential oils derived from fruits of *Laurus nobilis*, are mainly used in soap manufacturing.

Laurus nobilis has a wide range of utilities in healing rheumatism, dermatitis, gastrointestinal issues. Its aqueous extract has been used as an anti-hemorrhoid, anti-

rheumatic and a diuretic due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, insect repellent, antibacterial and acaricidal activities.

Essential oil obtained from *Laurus nobilis* is known to have the following chemical constituents which are presented in the Figure 2.4. It contains 1,8- Cineole, eugenol, α -terpinyl acetate, terpinene-4-ol, α -pinene, α -terpinyl acetate, β -pinene, linalool acetate, dimethylstyrene, (E)- β -cymene, p-cymene, β -longipinene, linalool, cadinene, α -bulnesene, myrcenol, terpinene-4-ol, sabinene, cuminaldehyde, methyl eugenol and carvacrol.

Figure 2.4: Chemical Constituents present in *Laurus N.* oil

2.2.3. *Bacopa monnieri*

Figure 2.5: Leaves of *Bacopa M.*

Table 2.3: Taxonomical Classification of *Bacopa monnieri*

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Lamiales
Family	Scrophulariaceae
Genus	Bacopa
Species	<i>Monnieri</i>

Bacopa monnieri, presented in Figure 2.5, is a herb found in the wetlands of India. It belongs to the genus Bacopa (Table 2.3), which includes over 100 aquatic herbs' species, which are distributed across India, Sri Lanka, China, Nepal, Vietnam and Taiwan.

Bacopa monnieri (Brahmi) has been used in Ayurveda as a revitalizing herb and is known as a Medhyarasayana, a drug known to improve memory and intellect. Formulations used in treating a range of mental conditions such as anxiety, poor cognition and lack of concentration have been documented in the Charakasamhita. It has also been recommended as a diuretic and an energizer for the nervous system and the heart.

Brahmi is used as an astringent, diuretic, laxative and a liquid suspension for the heart, nerves and bronchitis system. It improves digestion, dispels poisonous infections, splenic disorders and blood impurities. Its pharmacological properties include sedative, tranquillizing properties, cognitive effects, antidepressant, anti-anxiety effects, anti-epilaptic effects, gastrointestinal effects and anti-oxidant properties.

Chemical constituents of the *Bacopa monnieri* oil, presented in Figure 2.6, contains Bacosaponin A, Bacosaponin B, Bacosaponin C, Bacopaside I, Bacopaside II, Bacopaside IV, Bacopaside V, Bacopasaponin D, Bacosaponin C, Bacoside A and Bacoside B.

Figure 2.6: Chemical Constituents present in *Bacopa monnieri* oil

2.2.4. *Hibiscus rosasinensis*

Figure 2.7: Flowers of *Hibiscus R.*

Table 2.4: Taxonomical Classification of *Hibiscus Rosa-senensis*

Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Super Division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Dilleniidae
Order	Malvales
Family	Malvaceae
Genus	Hibiscus
Species	<i>rosa-sinensis</i>

Hibiscus rosasinensis, commonly known as Chinese hibiscus is a flowering plant belonging to the family, Malvaceae (Table 2.4.) and has the characteristics of a bushy, evergreen shrub.

Hair loss is a dermatological disorder. It is mainly caused due to psychological and physical distress, revolving around mass production of androgens in the body. *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers (Figure 2.7) were mainly used for the manufacture of Shampoo.

Its pharmacological uses include abortifacient effect, barbiturate potentiation, acid phosphate stimulation, β gluconidase activity, alkaline phosphate inhibition, β gluconidase stimulation, analgesic activity, etc.

Hibiscus rosasinensis contains various chemical constituents (shown in Figure 2.8) such as Cyaniding diglucoside, flavonoids and vitamins, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin and ascorbic acid, quercetin-3-diglucoside, 3,7-diglucoside, cyanidin-3,5-diglucoside, cyaniding-3-sophoroside-5-glucoside, etc.

Figure 2.8: Chemical constituents present in *Hibiscus R.* oil

CHAPTER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY USED

In the present work we have used leaves of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.* and *Bacopa M.* and flowers of *Hibiscus R.* as plant materials and Ethanol, Benzene, Petroleum Ether and Chloroform as solvents for the essential oil extraction.

3.1. MATERIALS USED

3.1.1 Plant material used

The leaves of *Mentha A.* were purchased from the Krishna Raja Market, Bengaluru, while leaves of *Laurus N.* and *Bacopa M.*, and flowers of *Hibiscus R.* were collected from a nearby farm.

3.1.2 Chemicals used

In the present work, we have used Benzene, Petroleum ether, Chloroform and Ethanol as solvents for essential oil extraction from plant material.

For quantitative analysis of the supernatant obtained upon Centrifugation, Phytochemical tests involved made use of distilled water, a 5 % FeCl₃ solution, Chloroform, Fehling's A, Fehling's B and Glacial Acetic Acid (procured from Merck Specialist Pvt. Ltd.), concentrated H₂SO₄ (procured from Fischer scientific), Ammonia solution (procured from Universal Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.), Methanol of HPLC grade (procured from Avantor), Dragendorff's reagent, Copper Acetate solution, alcoholic NaOH, and Millon's reagent (procured from Spectrum reagent and chemicals Pvt. Ltd.).

For the characterization of sample using TLC, we used n-Hexane (procured from Sisco laboratories Pvt. Ltd.), Petroleum Ether of Analytical grade was (procured from SDFCL), Toluene, Ethyl Acetate of Guaranteed reagent grade (procured from Merck Specialist Pvt. Ltd.), Ethanol, Formic acid, and Methanol.

3.1.3 Equipments used

Thin layer chromatography aluminum plates coated with Silica gel procured from Merck Specialist was used for the identification of compounds.

Soxhlet extractor of 1.0 liter capacity and simple distillation column of 0.5 liter capacity procured from Lab star instruments were used as a experimental set up for extraction and distillation. Centrifugation unit procured from Remi Make was used to centrifuge the sample after simple distillation.

3.2 METHODOLOGY FOLLOWED

According to the literature survey we were able to notice that for the extraction of essential oils using Soxhlet method was optimum, when compared to other methods like Steam Distillation.

Initially the leaves and flowers collected was subjected for Pre-treatment, followed by solvent extraction of essential oils from the pre treated and crushed crude plant material using Soxhlet extractor using a suitable solvent. After extraction the compound extracted have to be separated from solvent, for this separation process we have employed simple distillation.

In simple distillation we have separated the solvent from the extracted liquid and the residue obtained was collected and subjected for centrifugation for multiple times to separate the essential oil from the concentrated solution.

For the analysis of the extracted compound Gas Chromatography, High Pressure Liquid Chromatography, Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy and Mass Spectrometry were usually used; in the present work we have used Thin layer chromatography and FTIR for identification of the extracted compounds.

The supernatant left after centrifugation was subjected for various phyto-chemical tests to determine the various compounds present in the supernatant.

CHAPTER 4

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND SETUP

The experimental design and setup pertaining to all our objectives has been depicted in the form of various flowcharts.

4.1 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The detailed experimental work is presented in the flowchart in Figure 4.1. Initially the collected plant materials were pre-treated and crushed by a drop weight crusher; the particles retained on the 22 mesh number screen were added to the Soxhlet extractor with the addition of an appropriate solvent. The extract obtained was subjected to Simple distillation for maximum evaporation of the solvent used for extraction, the residue thus obtained, was subjected to centrifugation, a multiple times in order to obtain concentrated essential oils. The essential oils thus obtained, were characterized using TLC and FT-IR spectroscopy, while the supernatant was subjected to phytochemical tests.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart for extraction of essential oils from *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.* and *Bacopa M.* leaves, and *Hibiscus R.* flowers

4.1.1 Pre-treatment of leaves and flowers

As shown in the Figure 4.2, the fresh plant materials (Leaves and flowers) collected were washed with tap water for 5 minutes to remove all the sand particles and other debris present within the plant materials and then washed with distilled water for 2 minutes. The washed samples were subjected for drying under sunlight for 4 days and then to homogenization in order to obtain coarse powder.

Figure 4.2: Pre-treatment of plant material collected

4.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

4.2.1 Soxhlet extraction

Soxhlet extraction unit which was procured from Lab Star Instruments, Mumbai, made up of Borosilicate material was used as a experimental setup. It consists of 500 ml of round bottom flask, which holds a spiral vertical condenser having a siphon attached to the round bottom flask. The complete unit was kept on the mantle which was heated to a prescribed temperature depending upon the solvent used for extraction. These components are placed one above another as depicted in the Figure 4.3. A saché containing coarse powder of plant material is placed in the extractor which contains a sealed thimble made of cellulose/filter paper. A suitable solvent is poured into the distillation flask and the heat source is switched on; the set temperature must be such that

the solvent vaporizes. These vapors move through the bypass arm, finally reaching the condenser where the solvent condenses and accumulates in the extractor. When the solvent level in the extractor reaches an appropriate height, it flows down the siphon and back into the distillation flask. This procedure occurs cyclically several times and therefore ensures efficient extraction.

Figure 4.3: Experimental setup for a Soxhlet Extractor

4.2.2 Extraction of *Mentha arvensis* oil

A saché containing 20 g of coarse powder of *Mentha A.* leaves were inserted into the Soxhlet Extractor presented in Figure 4.4, and 250 ml of Ethanol was added. The unit was allowed to run for 10 hrs at 78°C, after which the extract was subjected to Simple distillation at 78.4°C, is shown in the Figure 4.5, in order to evaporate the ethanol and to concentrate the *Mentha A.* crude oil. The vapors obtained was condensed and reused as Ethanol, while the residue obtained was further subjected to centrifugation for multiple times (4 times) initially at 6000 rpm for 2 min, then at 10000 rpm for 5 min (twice) and

finally at 10000 rpm for 10 min, in order to obtain concentrated essential oil. The pellet obtained was collected (Shown in Fig 4.7) and subjected for TLC and FT-IR analysis, while the supernatant collected presented in Figure 4.6 was subjected for Phytochemically analysis for the presence of chemical constituents that were leached out from the essential oil.

4.2.3 Extraction of *Laurus nobilis* oil

A saché containing 20 g of coarse powder of *Laurus N.* leaves was inserted into the Soxhlet Extractor (Figure 4.8) and 250 ml of Benzene was added. The unit was allowed to run for 10 hrs at 80°C, after which the extract obtained was subjected to Simple distillation (Shown in the Figure 4.9) at 80.1°C, in order to evaporate Benzene and to concentrate the *Laurus N.* crude oil, while the residue obtained was further subjected to centrifugation for multiple times (4 times) initially at 6000 rpm for 2 min, then at 10000 rpm for 2 min, then at 10000 rpm for 4 min and finally at 10000 rpm for 5 min, in order to obtain concentrated essential oil. The pellet obtained (Figure 4.10) was collected and subjected for TLC and FT-IR analysis, while the supernatant collected (Figure 4.11) was Phytochemically analyzed for the presence of chemical constituents that were leached out from the essential oil.

4.2.4 Extraction of *Bacopa monnieri* oil

A saché containing 20 g of coarse powder of *Bacopa M.* leaves was inserted into the Soxhlet Extractor (Shown in Figure 4.12) and 250 ml of Ethanol was added. The unit was allowed to run for 10 hrs at 78°C, after which the extract was subjected to Simple distillation (Shown in the Figure 4.13) at 78.4°C, in order to evaporate Ethanol and to concentrate the *Bacopa M.* crude oil, while the residue obtained was further subjected to centrifugation for multiple times (4 times) initially at 6000 rpm for 2 min, then at 10000 rpm for 4 min, then at 10000 rpm for 5 min and finally at 10000 rpm for 10 min, in order to obtain concentrated essential oil. The pellet (Figure 4.15) obtained was collected and subjected for TLC and FT-IR analysis, while the supernatant (Figure 4.14) collected was Phytochemically analyzed for the presence of chemical constituents that were leached out from the essential oil.

4.2.5 Extraction of *Hibiscus rosasinensis* oil

A saché containing 20 g of coarse powder of *Hibiscus R.* flowers was inserted into the Soxhlet Extractor (Shown in Figure 4.16) and 250 ml of Ethanol was added. The unit was allowed to run for 10 hrs at 78°C, after which the extract was subjected to Simple distillation (Shown in the Figure 4.17) at 78.4°C to evaporate Ethanol and to concentrate the *Hibiscus R.* crude oil, while the residue obtained was further subjected to centrifugation for multiple times (3 times) each at 10000 rpm for 5 min, in order to obtain concentrated essential oil. The pellet obtained (Figure 4.19) was collected and subjected for TLC and FT-IR analysis, while the supernatant collected (Figure 4.18) was Phytochemically analyzed for the presence of chemical constituents that were leached out from the essential oil.

Figure 4.4. Soxhlet extraction of essential oil from *Mentha A*

Figure 4.5. Simple distillation of ethanolic extract of *Mentha A.* oil

Figure 4.6: Supernatant obtained upon concentration of *Mentha A.* oil

Figure 4.7: *Mentha A.* crude oil

Figure 4.8: Soxhlet extraction *Laurus N.* oil

Figure 4.9: Simple distillation of benzene extract of *Laurus N.* oil

Figure 4.10: Supernatant obtained upon concentration of *Laurus N.* oil

Figure 4.11: *Laurus N.* crude oil

Figure 4.12: Soxhlet extraction of *Bacopa M.* oil

Figure 4.13: Simple Distillation of Ethanolic extract of *Bacopa M.* oil

Figure 4.14: Supernatant obtained upon concentration of *Bacopa M.* oil

Figure 4.15: *Bacopa M.* crude oil

Figure 4.16: Soxhlet extraction of *Hibiscus R.* oil

Figure 4.17: Steam Distillation of Ethanolic extract of *Hibiscus R.* oil

Figure 4.18: Supernatant obtained upon concentration of *Hibiscus R.* oil

Figure 4.19: *Hibiscus R.* crude oil

4.2.6 Phytochemical test

After the extraction of essential oils the supernatant was retained and subjected for phytochemical tests presented in the Table 4.1, for the analysis of compounds present in the supernatant.

Table 4.1: Quality assessment of essential oils using Phytochemical Tests

Test for compound	Procedure	Observation
Tannins	2 drops of 5% FeCl ₃ solution was added to 2 ml of extract	A blue-black precipitate formation implies that the extract contains tannins.
Saponins	5 ml of distilled water was added to 0.5 ml of extract and the test tube, shake it vigorously.	If it results in a stable persistent froth, then it shows a positive reaction.
Terpenoids	0.5 ml of extract was taken in a test tube. 2 ml of Chloroform and 3 ml of conc. H ₂ SO ₄ was added.	The formation of a reddish brown ring shows the presence of Terpenoids.

Isolation, extraction and characterization of essential oils from *Mentha arvensis*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Bacopa monnieri* leaves and *Hibiscus rosasinensis* flowers

Cardiac Glycosides	1 ml of Glacial Acetic acid, containing 1 drop of FeCl ₃ was added to 2 ml of extract. The solution was then poured into a test tube containing 1 ml of conc. Sulphuric acid.	Brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of deoxysugar, which is a characteristic of Caedenolides. The presence of violet and green rings may occur.
Anthraquinones	10 ml of H ₂ SO ₄ was added to a test tube containing 0.5 ml of extract. The contents were filtered while it was hot and 5 ml of Chloroform was added to the filtrate.	The chloroform layer was transferred to another test tube to observe any changes.
Flavonoids	1ml of conc. Sulphuric acid was added to the extract, followed by 5 ml of dil. Ammonia.	The presence of a yellow colouration that disappears on standing, gives a positive result for Flavonoids Test.
Steroids	10 ml of Chloroform and 10 ml of Sulphuric acid was added to 1 ml of the extract.	A positive result shows formation of a brick-red layer, along with an upper yellow layer.
Polysterol	10 ml of Chloroform and 10 ml of Sulphuric acid was added to 1 ml of the extract.	A positive result shows formation of a brick-red layer, along with an upper yellow layer.
Phenol	1 ml of FeCl ₃ was added to 2 ml of extract.	A blueish green colour suggests the presence of Phenol.

Alkaloids	0.2 ml of methanolic extract was taken and 2% conc. H ₂ SO ₄ solution was added to it. It was filtered after heating it for 2 min. Dragendorff's reagent was added drop-wise to the filtrate.	Formation of an orange-red precipitate indicates the presence of Alkaloids.
Diterpenes	The extract was dissolved in water and 10 drops of Copper Acetate solution was added.	Formation of an emerald green colour shows the presence of Diterpenes.
Coumarins	Alcoholic NaOH was added to 2 ml of sample.	Formation of a yellow colour shows a positive test.
Carbohydrates	1ml each of Fehling's A and B was added to 2ml of sample and warmed for 15 minutes.	Formation of reddish-brown precipitate confirms as a positive test.
Proteins	2 drops of Millon's reagent was added to 5 drops of sample and warmed for 15 minutes.	Formation of a dark red precipitate confirms the test.

4.2.7 Thin layer chromatography

In the present work we have used Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) plates manufactured by Merck. The TLC plates contain silica gel coated on aluminum foil. Each TLC plate measures around 6 cm in breadth and 10 cm in height. We have chosen different solvents as a mobile phase for different essential oils as shown the Table 4.2 below. The extract was spotted on the TLC plate and placed in a chamber which has mobile phase as shown in the Figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Thin Layer Chromatography

Table 4.2: Name of the extract with mobile phases used for TLC analysis is mentioned

Sl. No	Name of the extract	Mobile phase	Ratio
1	<i>Mentha arvensis</i> oil	n-Hexane: Petroleum Ether	(10:1)
2	<i>Laurus nobilis</i> oil	Toluene: Ethyl acetate	(1:20)
3	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> oil	Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Ethanol: Formic acid	(3:4:3:1)
4	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i> oil	Petroleum Ether: n-Hexane: Chloroform: Methanol	(18:1.5:1.5:0.5) (6:2:2:3)

4.2.8 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

A newly invented technique in organic chemistry to identify the functional groups present in the chemical compound is FT-IR. An identity of a pure compound can be found using this method. Certain frequencies occur in the infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum which is around 4000 cm^{-1} to 200 cm^{-1} , which is ideal for the working of an FT-IR instrument.

4.2.8.1 Working mechanism of FT-IR

When a beam of infrared light is passed through a sample it would absorb certain amount of radiation, while transmitting all of the other frequencies. An infrared spectrometer is used to measure the frequencies of absorbed radiation resulting in the formation of an infrared spectrum, which is made by plotting absorbed energy vs frequency. Due to different vibrations exhibited by various materials, a variety of spectra are obtained. The concentration of that chemical species present in the sample is related to the magnitude of its absorption.

The infrared source emits a broadband of different wavelengths in the infrared spectrum. The interferometer modulates the infrared radiation and passes the modulated IR beam through the gas sample where it is absorbed at different wavelengths by the various molecules present in the sample (Figure 4.21). The IR spectrum of the sample gas is obtained after it is Fourier transformed by the computer. Mercury Cadmium Telluride is the most commonly used detector for FT-IR analysis.

For FTIR 40 μl of sample of essential oil extracted was kept on the sample holder and operated the equipment at a wave length of $1000\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure 4.21: Working principle behind FT-IR analysis

Table 4.3 specifies the instrument details of FT-IR spectrophotometer used to conduct the characterization of essential oils obtained from leaves of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.* and *Bacopa M.*, and flowers of *Hibiscus R.*

Table 4.3: Instrument details of FT-IR Spectrophotometer used for the characterization analysis

Instrument Model	Frontier FT-IR
Instrument Serial Number	94887
Software Revision	CPU32 Main 00.09.9951 07-September-2011 11:49:41
Resolutions	4
Number of Scans	4
Detector	LiTa03
Source	MIR
Beamsplitter	OptKBr
Apodization	Strong
Spectrum Type	Spectrum
Beam Type	Ratio
Phase correction	Magnitude
Scan Speed	0.5
IGram Type	Double
Scan Direction	Combined
Zero Crossings	0
JStop	8.94
IR-Laser Wavenumber	15798.00
Manufacturer	PES6
Part Number	L1250240
Serial Number	33766
Description	DATR 1 bounce Diamond/ZnSe
Default Scan Range / cm⁻¹	4000 – 650
Force Applied / N	69
Accessory Type	Universal ATR
UATR Crystal Combination	Diamond/ZnSe
UATR Number of Bounces	1
UATR Option	Not Specified

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results obtained from the experiments performed as described in Chapter 4 were discussed along with appropriate images. The interpretations of the observed data are discussed with scientific basis as per literature which share data concordance.

5.1 RESULTS OF EXTRACTION OF ESSENTIAL OILS

The results of extraction of essential oils using Soxhlet extractor, Simple Distillation and Centrifugation are presented in the Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Yield percentage of extracted oils obtained from different plant material

Sl. No.	Plant material	Initial amount of material (g)	Name of the oil extracted	Yield in %
1	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	20	Cornmint oil	6.25
2	<i>Laurus nobilis</i>		Bay Laurel oil	5.47
3	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>		Brahmi oil	8.45
4	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i>		Hibiscus oil	4.05

From the table it is noticed that the percentage of yield of Cornmint oil is 6.25%, Bay laurel oil is 5.47 %, Brahmi oil is 8.45 % and Hibiscus oil is 4.05 %. The percentage of yield of Brahmi oil is higher in comparison to the others.

5.2 PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

5.2.1 *Mentha arvensis*

Upon subjecting the supernatant obtained through DSP of Cornmint Oil to qualitative analysis via Phytochemical tests (Shown in Figure 5.1), it was observed that most of the constituents had leached out of the oil. The experimental results were in concordance with those documented in the literature (Table 5.2).

Table 5.2: Results of Phytochemical analysis of Cornmint Oil

Test conducted for the compounds	Results found in Literature	Results found in Experiment
Alkaloids	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Phenols	+	+
Tannins	+	+
Saponins	-	-
Diterpenes	+	+
Cardiac glycosides	+	+

From the results obtained from Table 5.2, Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Phenol, Tannins, Saponins, Diterpenes and Cardiac Glycosides are present in the supernatant of the *Mentha arvensis*.

Figure 5.1: Phytochemical analysis of Cornmint Oil

5.2.2 *Laurus nobilis*

Upon subjecting the supernatant obtained through DSP of Bay laurel Oil to qualitative analysis via Phytochemical tests (Shown in Figure 5.2), it was observed that most of the constituents had leached out of the oil. The experimental results were in concordance with those documented in the literature (Table 5.3).

Table 5.3: Results of Phytochemical analysis of Bay laurel Oil

Test conducted for the compounds	Results found in Literature	Results found in Experiment
Reducing Sugar	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Phenols	+	+
Saponins	-	-
Tannins	+	+
Protein	+	+
Anthroquinone	-	-
Flavonoids	+	+
Alkaloids	-	-

From the results obtained from Table 5.3, Terpenoids, Flavonoids, Phenol, Tannins, Proteins and Cardiac Glycosides are present in the supernatant of the *Laurus nobilis*.

Figure 5.2: Phytochemical analysis of Bay laurel Oil

5.2.3 *Bacopa monnieri*

Upon subjecting the supernatant obtained through DSP of Brahmi Oil to qualitative analysis via Phytochemical tests (Shown in Figure 5.3), it was observed that most of the constituents had leached out of the oil. The experimental results were in concordance with those documented in the literature (Table 5.4).

Table 5.4: Results of Phytochemical analysis of Brahmi Oil

Test conducted for the compounds	Results found in Literature	Results found in Experiment
Tannins	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Glycosides	-	-
Flavonoids	+	-
Steroids	+	+
Polysterol	+	+
Phenolic	-	+
Anthroquinone	-	-

From the results obtained from Table 5.4, Terpenoids, Saponins, Steroids, Polysterol, Phenol and Tannins are present in the supernatant of the *Bacopa monnieri*.

Figure 5.3: Phytochemical analysis of Brahmi Oil

5.2.4 *Hibiscus rosasinensis*

Upon subjecting the supernatant obtained through DSP of Hibiscus Oil to qualitative analysis via Phytochemical tests (Shown in Figure 5.4), it was observed that most of the constituents had leached out of the oil. The experimental results were in concordance with those documented in the literature (Table 5.5).

Table 5.5: Results of Phytochemical analysis of Hibiscus Oil

Test conducted for the compounds	Results found in Literature	Results found in Experiment
Alkaloids	+	+
Carbohydrates	-	-
Coumarins	+	-
Steroids	-	-
Tannins	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Proteins	-	-
Anthroquinones	-	-
Phenols	-	+

From the results obtained from Table 5.5, Alkaloids, Saponins, Flavonoids, Phenol and Tannins are present in the supernatant of the *Hibiscus rosasinensis*.

Figure 5.4: Phytochemical analysis of Hibiscus Oil

5.3 THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY

The results of the TLC analysis obtained from the experiments, conducted as mentioned in the Chapter 4.0, using various solvents mentioned in Table 4.2, for the various essential oils mentioned in the Table 5, are depicted from the Figures 5.5 to 5.10.

5.3.1 *Mentha arvensis*

The results of TLC of the Cornmint oil are presented in the Figure 5.5. From the figure, we can identify the compounds such as Terpene ester and Menthol which are represented by a Yellow and Blue dot respectively. R_f values of 0.67 and 0.25 are obtained (Table 5.6).

Figure 5.5: TLC Result obtained for Cornmint oil

Table 5.6: R_f values of the compounds present in the Cornmint oil

Extract used	Compound Name	Colour	R_f value
Chloroform: Methanol	Terpene ester	Yellow	0.67
Chloroform: Methanol	Menthol	Blue	0.25

5.3.2 *Laurus nobilis*

The results of TLC analysis Bay Laurel oil extracted from *Laurus nobilis* leaves are depicted in Figure 5.6. From the figure, we can clearly note the presence of different constituents of Bay laurel oil, which are depicted in shades of Blue to light green, corresponding to R_f values between 0.71 and 0.821 (Table 5.7).

Figure 5.6: TLC results obtained for Bay laurel oil

Table 5.7: R_f value of the Bay Laurel oil extracted

Extract used	Colour	R _f value
Benzene	Blue	0.71
Benzene	Yellow	0.76
Benzene	Light Green	0.821

5.3.3 *Bacopa monnieri*

The result of TLC analysis of Brahmi oil is depicted in Figure 5.7. From the TLC plate, we can clearly identify the compound Bacoside A at an R_f value of 0.45, corresponding to a Brown colour (Table 5.8).

Figure 5.7: TLC result obtained for Brahmi Oil

Table 5.8: R_f value of compound Bacoside A present in Brahmi oil.

Extract used	Compound Name	Colour	R _f value
Ethanol	Bacoside A	Brown	0.45

5.3.4 *Hibiscus rosasinensis*

Hibiscus oil obtained from hibiscus flowers was subjected to TLC analysis, twice. The results obtained are depicted in Figures 5.8 and 5.9. The Figure 5.8 indicates the presence of compound n-Pentacosane at an R_f value of 0.69, corresponding to a Yellow spot (Table 5.10), upon using Petroleum ether for extract preparation. Figure 5.9 indicates the presence of compounds D-3-epl-taraxareyl and Taraxerylacetate represented at R_f values of 0.69 and 0.76, corresponding to Orange and Green spots, respectively (Table 5.9) upon using Petroleum ether: Chloroform at a ratio of 95:5 (v/v) for extract preparation. Both the TLC analyses make use of a mobile phase having Petroleum Ether: n-Hexane: Chloroform: Methanol at ratios (18:1.5:1.5:0.5) and (6:2:2:3).

Figure 5.8. TLC results for Hibiscus oil using Petroleum Ether: Hexane: Chloroform: Methanol (18:1.5:1.5:0.5)

Figure 5.9. TLC results for Hibiscus oil using a mobile phase of Petroleum Ether: Hexane: Chloroform: Methanol (6:2:2:3)

Table 5.9: R_f values documented for compounds that were successfully isolated from Hibiscus oil, using TLC

Extract used	Compound Name	Colour	R_f value
PE	n-Pentacosane	Yellow	0.69
PE: Chloroform	D-3-epl-taraxareyl	Orange	0.69
PE: Chloroform	Taraxerylacetate	Green	0.76

5.4 FT-IR SPECTROSCOPY

The essential oils obtained from the Soxhlet extractor, simple distillation and centrifugation were subjected for characterization using FT-IR Spectrometer at R&D centre, R.V.C.E, Bengaluru.

5.4.1 *Mentha arvensis*

Figure 5.10: FT-IR analysis of Cornmint Oil

In the Figure 5.10 we can observe O-H vibrations at 2917.13 cm⁻¹, 2974.38 cm⁻¹ and 3359.80 cm⁻¹ were seen; thus indicating the presence of Carboxylic Acid and Alcohols, respectively. C=O vibration, indicative of Amide groups, was observed at 1651.65 cm⁻¹. Bending vibrations at 1452.13 cm⁻¹ and 1378.69 cm⁻¹, indicative of C-H bond, confirms the presence of Alkanes. Vibrations at 1044.84 cm⁻¹ and 1087.05 cm⁻¹, indicates the presence of C-O bond, which is a confirmation for presence of Alcohols, Ethers, Ester, Carboxylic acid and anhydrides. Out of plane bends, aromatic compounds are indicated by vibrations at 878.9 cm⁻¹. Additionally, vibrations at 1269.19 cm⁻¹ indicated S=O,

which confirms the presence of Sulphones, Sulphonyl Chlorides, Sulphate and Sulphonamides.

5.4.2 *Laurus nobilis*

Figure 5.11: FT-IR analysis of Bay laurel Oil

From the above Figure 5.11 we can observe stretch vibrations at 3036.01 cm⁻¹, 3071.84 cm⁻¹ and 3091.29 cm⁻¹, which indicate the presence of C-H bonds, which correspond to Alkenes. Vibrations were observed at 1478.28 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of C=C bond, which refer to Aromatic compounds. Anhydrides, indicated by C=O bond, is observed at vibrations occurring at 1814.04 cm⁻¹. Vibration occurring at 1958.87 cm⁻¹, indicates presence of X=C=Y bond which refers to presence of Allenes, Ketenes, Isocyanates and Isothiocyanates. Vibrations occurring at 668.96 cm⁻¹ and 1034.93 cm⁻¹, show the presence of Chlorides and Fluorides.

5.4.3 *Bacopa monnieri*

Figure 5.12: FT-IR analysis of Brahmi oil

From the above Figure 5.12 we can observe the vibrations at 2850.09 cm^{-1} , referring to C-H bond which indicates the presence of Aldehyde. Additionally, bend vibrations were observed at 1376.42 cm^{-1} and 1462.61 cm^{-1} , referring to C-H which shows the presence of Alkanes, specifically $-\text{CH}_3-$ and $-\text{CH}_2-$, respectively. Vibrations at 2164.70 cm^{-1} and 1634.57 cm^{-1} , refer to $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds, thus indicating the presence of Alkynes and Alkenes. Vibrations at 2918.31 cm^{-1} and 3352.35 cm^{-1} , indicate presence of O-H bonds, which refer to Carboxylic acid and Alcohol, Phenols. Vibrations at 649.59 cm^{-1} and 1037.19 cm^{-1} , indicate the presence of Chlorides and Fluorides.

5.4.4 *Hibiscus rosasinensis*

Figure 5.13: FT-IR analysis of Hibiscus Oil

From the above Figure 5.13 we can observe that bend and out of phase vibrations were seen at 1384.92 cm^{-1} and 877.89 cm^{-1} , referring to C-H bond, indicating the presence of Alkanes and Aromatics, respectively. Vibrations at 1645.99 cm^{-1} , 2151.03 cm^{-1} and 2979.58 cm^{-1} , correspond to C=C, C≡C and O-H bonds, thus indicating the presence of Alkenes, Alkynes and Carboxylic acids, respectively. Vibrations were also seen at 1043.99 cm^{-1} , referring to C-O bond, thus indicating the presence of Alcohols, Ethers, Esters, Carboxylic Acids and Anhydrides. Furthermore, vibrations at 1085.36 cm^{-1} and 618.56 cm^{-1} , refer to C-N bond and C-X bond, thus indicating the presence of Amines and Chlorides. Stretch vibrations at 3322.24 cm^{-1} , refer to N-H bond, thus indicating the presence of Primary and Secondary Amines and Amides.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

The following sections deals with a brief explanation of the conclusions made from this study, it also highlights various futuristic possibilities that can be investigated upon research along the same lines.

6.1 CONCLUSION

The study elaborates on the steps involved in DSP of essential oils obtained from leaves of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.* and *Bacopa M.*, and flowers of *Hibiscus R.*

- The primary objective was to adopt the most efficient of the DSP methodologies for maximum extraction of essential oils. We began with vacuum distillation as our primary equipment for the extraction process and proceeded to incorporate steam distillation, before considering the Soxhlet extraction process. Upon Soxhlet extraction, the extract was subjected to simple distillation, followed by characterization of the resultant essential oil using TLC. As the essential oil was heavily diluted and still in its extract form, another concentration step- Centrifugation, was introduced into the DSP of essential oils.
- A crude sample of an essential oil is said to homogenous only if it exists in a solid or a liquid form. Since most of the chemical constituents are present in concentrations of 0.05-0.2%, their detection within the sample becomes fruitless. Therefore, the centrifugation step was utilized mainly for the concentration of the oil. Several permutations and combinations of centrifugal speed and their durations were taken into account in order to obtain pellets.
- The supernatant thus obtained were tested for the presence of Terpenoids, Diterpenes, Triterpenoids, Glycosides, Cardiac glycosides, Saponins, Tannins, Phenolic compounds, Steroids, Polyesterols, Proteins, Carbohydrates, Anthraquinones, Flavonoids and Alkaloids via qualitative analysis.
- Crude samples of essential oils thus obtained were subjected to TLC analysis. The analysis of *Mentha A.* crude oil obtained upon using Chloroform as a solvent, showed the presence of Pulegone at $R_f = 0.47$, when a chloroform extract and n-Hexane:

Petroleum Ether mobile phase were used. Pulegone marked a crucial discovery during the project, as it is a Neuro-toxin.

- Characterization using FT-IR spectroscopy showed the presence of Alcohols, Phenols, Carboxylic acids, Aromatic compounds, Alkanes, Alkenes, Allenes, Ketenes, Isocyanates, Isothiocyanates and in some cases, even Halogens, such as Chlorides and Fluorides.

6.2 SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

Mentha A, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* leaves and *Hibiscus R.* flowers are known to contain numerous medicinal properties; various formulations of their oils along with carrier oils are now being used in research work in Aromatherapy, Reflexology, Bath and body works, and even in tablets.

Phytochemical, TLC and FT-IR analyses enhance the understanding of chemical constituents present within the oils extracted. Further analysis with GC-MS gives us an insight into the composition and can aide in testing their pharmacological properties.

Pulegone, a neurotoxin was accidentally extracted during the DSP of Cornmint oil using Chloroform as the solvent of interest, and so was Bacoside A, during DSP of Brahmi oil. Bacoside A is known to have a cure for Parkinson's disease. The forthcoming investigations can involve accidental discoveries made during the course of the project.

Additionally, anti- microbial profiles for essential oils and their neurological effects on humans can be scrutinized.

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APPENDIX A

The results of qualitative analysis of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* and *Hibiscus R.* oils using Phytochemical tests as explained in the research papers, have been illustrated in this Appendix.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *MENTHA A.* OIL

The qualitative phytochemical investigation of various extracts of leaves, stems and roots of *Mentha A.* showed the presence of different phytochemical compounds, such as Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Polyphenols, Tannins, Cardiac Glycosides, which indicate their distribution in the whole plant (Table A.1). Test for Saponins showed their absence from leaves, stem and root extracts. Furthermore, results indicate that Diterpenes are present in leaves and stem extracts, while absent in root extracts. [42]

Table A.1: Qualitative analysis of secondary phytochemicals present in extracts of *Mentha A.*

S/N	Phytochemicals	Name of the test	Leaves	Stem	Root
1	Alkaloids	Dragendorff's test	+	+	+
		Wagner's test	+	+	+
2	Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent test	+	+	+
		Lead acetate test	+	+	+
3	Phenols	Ferric chloride test	+	+	+
4	Tannins	Geltin test	+	+	+
5	Saponins	Froth test	-	-	-
		Foam test	-	-	-
6	Diterpenes	copper acetate test	+	+	-
7	Cardiac glycosides	Modified Borntrager's test	+	+	+

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *LAURUS N.* OIL

The qualitative assays for tannins, reducing sugars, phenols and flavonoids were followed by Sofowara,^[60] Trease and Evans^[61] and Harborne^[62], for Mustard, Bay leaf, Ajwain, Cardamom, Pepper, Cloves, Cumin, Methi, Cinnamon and Saunf. The proteins, tannins and reducing sugars are the primary metabolites of plants, necessary for cellular processes while phenols and flavonoids are secondary metabolic compounds produced in

response to stress, such as the case when acting as a deterrent against herbivores as mentioned by Kim. [63]

Table A.2: Qualitative analysis of secondary phytochemicals present in various spices

Botanical Name	Common name	Reducing sugar	cardiac glycosides	Terpenoids	Saponins	Tannins	Phenol	Proteins	Anthraquinones	Flavonoid	Alkaloids
Brassica nigra	Mustard	+	+	+	+	+	++	+	-	+	+
Laurus nobilis	Bay leaf	-	++	++	-	+	+	+	-	+	-
Trachyspermum copticum	Ajwain	+	++	++	-	++	++	+	-	+	+
Elettaria cardamomum	Cardamom	+	+	++	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
piper nigrum	Pepper	+	++	++	-	-	-	+	-	+	+
Syzygium aromaticum	Cloves	+	+	++	+	++	++	+	-	+	+
Cuminum cyminum	Cumin	+	++	++	-	++	++	+	-	+	-
Trigonella foenum graecum	Methi	+	+	++	+	+	+	+	-	++	+
Cinnamomum verum	Cinnamon	+	++	++	-	++	+	+	-	+	-
Foeniculum vulgare	Saunf	+	++	++	-	-	+	+	-	+	-

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *BACOPA M.* OIL

Preliminary phytochemical screening for the presence of Tannins, Saponins, Phenolics, Terpenoids, Steroids, Polysterol, Anthraquinone, Glycosides and Flavonoids were illustrated by Harbone. [62] In the present study, preliminary phytochemical tests on the leaf callus ethanolic and aqueous extract revealed the presence of Tannins, Saponins, Terpenoids, Steroids and Polysterol, and the absence of Anthraquinone and Phenolics in both. Furthermore, the presence of Glycosides was seen in the aqueous extract, while that of Flavonoids was seen in the ethanolic extract.

Table A.3: Qualitative analysis of secondary phytochemicals present in extracts of *Bacopa M.*

Sl No.	Phytochemical(Test)	Ethanol	Aqueous
1.	Tannins	+	+
2.	Saponins	+	+
3.	Terpenoids	+	+
4.	Glycosides	-	+
5.	Anthroquione	-	-
6.	Flavanoids	+	-
7.	Steroids	+	+
8.	Phytosterol	+	+
9.	Phenolic	-	-

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *HIBISCUS R.* OIL

Preliminary phytochemical analysis for Alkaloids, Triterpenoids, Coumarins, Tannins, Saponins and Flavonoids were found to be positive. ^[16]

Table A.4: Qualitative analysis of secondary phytochemicals present in extracts of *Hibiscus R.*

Chemical constituents	Tests	Flower maceration extract	Flower soxhlation extract	Flower water extract
1. Alkaloids	Wagner test	present	present	present
	Hager test	present	present	present
	Dragendorff's test	present	present	present
2. Carbohydrates	Fehling's test	absent	absent	absent
	Barfoed's test	absent	absent	absent
	Molisch test	absent	absent	absent
3. Triterpenoids	Salkowski test	present	present	absent
	Liebermann test	present	present	absent
4. Coumarins	10% NAOH	present	present	present
5. Steroids	Liebermann test	present	absent	absent
6. Tannins	5% FeCl ₃	present	present	present
7. Saponins	Water	absent	present	present
8. Flavones	Schinoda test	present	present	present
9. Chalcones	Conc. HNO ₃ & H ₂ SO ₄	absent	absent	absent
	Acetic acid & conc. H ₂ SO ₄	absent	absent	absent
10. Amino acids	Ninhydrin	absent	absent	absent
11. Glycosides	Keller kiliani test	absent	absent	absent
	Anthraquinone test	absent	absent	absent
12. Proteins	Biuret test	absent	absent	absent
	Million's test	absent	absent	absent
	Xanthoprotein test	absent	absent	absent
13. Phenols	10% FeCl ₃	absent	absent	absent
	Dil. HNO ₃	absent	absent	absent

APPENDIX B

The TLC results of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* and *Hibiscus R.* oils, mentioned in the research papers, have been illustrated in this Appendix.

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY ANALYSIS OF MENTHA A. OIL

Thin layer chromatography analysis was performed for a *Mentha A.* extract by using different solvent systems. Alcohols were identified by using benzene and methanol solution in the ratio of 10:1 and the observations are illustrated in the Table B.1. For ester identification benzene was used as a suitable solvent and the compounds identified are shown in the Table B.2, a mixture of n-hexane and ether in the ratio of 20:3 was used for the identification of carbonyl compounds which is illustrated in Table B.3. For the identification of the terpenoids the TLC plate was sprayed with 1% Vanillin reagent and the observations were recorded.

Table B.1: Thin layer Chromatography of Alcohols

Compounds	Sensi- tivity γ	Color Observed		Relative R_f Value*
		Room Temperature	After Heating	
Limonene diol	1	Faint pink	Deep pink	0.31
Geraniol	5	Grayish purple	Faint violet	0.72
<i>trans-p</i> -Menthadiene-2,8-ol-1	5	Faint blue	Blue black	0.80
Nerol	5	Bluish green	Violet	0.82
Citronellol	1	Faint violet	Violet	0.86
<i>trans</i> -Carveol	1	Violet	Violet	0.95
Dihydro Carveol	1	Faint violet	Bluish violet	0.98
Isopiperitenol	5	Faint blue	Deep blue	0.98
Perillyl Alcohol	5	Faint blue	Deep blue	0.98
α -Terpineol	1	Faint violet	Violet	1.00
<i>cis-p</i> -Menthadiene-1(7),8-ol-2	5	Faint blue	Blue black	1.00
<i>cis</i> -Carveol	1	Violet	Violet	1.01
Menthol	10	...	Faint violet	1.02
β -Terpineol	1	Faint violet	Violet	1.04
Linalool	1	Faint violet	Violet	1.06
Borneol	20	...	Faint grey	1.07
Isopulegol	1	Faint brown	Violet	1.12
β -Fenchyl Alcohol	5	Orange	Reddish brown	1.25
Carvomenthol	100	Faint green	Deep green	1.26
Neomenthol	10	Faint grey	Faint violet	1.28
α -Fenchyl Alcohol	100	...	Faint violet	1.30

Table B.2: Thin layer Chromatography of esters

Compound	Sensitivity	Color Observed	Relative
	γ		R_f Value ^a
Geranyl Acetate	2	Faint blue	1.00
Linalyl Acetate	2	Faint blue	1.13
Isobornyl Acetate	10	Orange	1.14
<i>trans</i> -Carveyl Acetate	2	Violet blue	1.17
Terpinyl Acetate	2	Faint blue	1.19
Bornyl Acetate	20	Faint purple	1.23
<i>cis</i> -Carveyl Acetate	2	Violet blue	1.28
Linalyl Formate	2	Faint blue	1.41
Menthyl Acetate	50	Violet blue ^b	1.46
Geranyl Formate	2	Faint blue	1.59
Menthyl Isovalerate	20	Deep blue ^b	2.08

Table B.3: Thin layer Chromatography of carbonyl compounds

Compounds	Sensitivity γ	Color Observed		Relative R_f Value ^a
		Room Temperature	After Heating	
Piperitenone	1	Faint purple	Faint blue	0.75
Piperitone	100	...	Saffron yellow	0.77
β -Ionone	1	Faint blue	Faint blue	0.78
Citral	10	Violet	Violet	0.82
γ -Ionone	1	Faint blue	Faint blue	0.92
Dihydrocitral	200	Violet blue	Violet blue	0.94
Carvone	1	...	Faint violet	1.00
Pulegone	10	Faint pink	Purple	1.00
α -Ionone	1	Faint blue	Faint blue	1.00
Carvomenthone	100	...	Faint pink	1.01
Methyl Heptenone	1	Faint violet	Green	1.02
Menthone	1000	...	Faint brown	1.17
Dihydrocarvone	200	Faint pink	Purple	1.36
Citronellal	1	...	Faint violet	1.47
Camphor	1000	Faint blue	Faint blue	1.72

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY ANALYSIS OF *BACOPA M.* OIL

The analysis of the components present in *Bacopa M.* extracts was done using toluene: ethyl acetate: methanol: formic acid in the ratio 3:4:3:1. The chloroform fraction was used for the isolation of Bacoside A. The TLC profile showed a single band indicating fairly pure compound.

Table B.4: Thin layer Chromatography of *Bacopa M.* extract

Sr.No	Mobile phase composition (v/v)				R _f	AUC
	Toluene	Ethyl acetate	Methanol	Formic acid		
1	3	4	2.5	1	0.44	15550.1 ±0.54
2	3	4	2.625	1	0.44	15487.66 ±0.47
3	3	4	2.375	1	0.44	15589.48 ±0.21
4	3	4	2.5	1.05	0.44	15471.06 ±0.61
5	3	4	2.5	0.95	0.44	15508.99 ±0.59
R.S.D.	-	-		-	0	0.31

Figure B.1: TLC of Bacoside A

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY ANALYSIS OF *LAURUS N.* OIL

The TLC sheet used was 0.25 mm thick and coated with silica gel. Laurel extracts were mixed with toluene and spotted on the plate. Mobile phase used was toluene: ethyl acetate. A Vanillin solution was prepared and sprayed on the sheet after the mobile phase is run to determine the compounds and observed under UV light.

Table B.5: TLC of *Laurus N.* extract

Compound	Color	hR _f value
Terpineol	Violet-blue	22.8
Linalool	Blue, green-blue	34.5
1,8-Cineole	Blue-violet	47.6
Terpineol acetate	Dark blue	70.2
α - and β -Pinene, Limonene	Rose, violet	96.9

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY ANALYSIS OF *HIBISCUS R.* OIL

TLC was performed on plates coated with Silica gel G (Qualigens). The dried plates were activated in an electric oven at 110° C for two hours. The dissolved fractions were spotted on the plates with the fine capillary tubes and then air dried. The spotted plates were kept in chromatographic chambers containing the solvent mixture and covered with greased glass plates. The TLC plates were visualized under UV light or exposure of plates to Iodine vapours or spraying with Ammonium Sulphate solution in 65% H₂SO₄ followed by keeping at 120° C for 10-15 minutes in an oven.

Different combinations of solvents were used and their results were observed.

Table B.6: TLC of Hibiscus extract

C o d e	Name	Column eluent	R _f mobile phase	Yield (%) w/w) Solvents used for recrystalli- zation	m.p. ^o C [α] _D ²⁸ value (CHCl ₃)	Mol. Wt. [M] ⁺ m/z [Mol. For].	Nomenclature
1	Aliphatic hydrocarbon	A	0.76 E	0.0128 by preparative chromatog- raphy	58-59 ^o	380 C ₂₇ H ₅₆	n-Pentacosane
2	3- <i>epi</i> - Taraxeryl acetate	A-B 95:5	0.75 F	0.011 B-D (1:1)	300-301 ^o (+) 152.6 (C=0.05)	468 C ₃₂ H ₅₂ O ₂	D- Friedo -olean -14 -en-3α- yl acetate (New)
3	Taraxeryl acetate	A-B 95:5	0.82 F	0.011 B-D (1:1)	303-305 ^o (+) 10.5 (C=1.5) at 23 ^o C	468 C ₃₂ H ₅₂ O ₂	D- Friedo -olean -14 -en-3β- yl acetate
4	Aliphatic alcohol	A-B 9:1	0.38 G	0.012 B-D (1:1)	74-78 ^o	576 C ₃₃ H ₆₈ O	n- Tritriacontan -1-ol (New)
5	Hibiscusyl ester	A-B 3:1	0.35 H	0.014 B-D (1:1)	90-91 ^o	450 C ₃₀ H ₅₈ O ₂	Cyclopentanyl carboxy-n- tetracosane (New)
6	Hibiscusol	A-B 3:1	0.34 H	0.01 B-D (1:1)	80-81 ^o	450 C ₃₁ H ₆₂ O	26- cyclopentyl n -hexacosan-5- ol. (New)

A = Petroleum ether, B = Chloroform, C= Hexane, D= Methanol
 E = Mobile phase (petroleum ether : hexane : chloroform : methanol ; 18: 1.5 : 1.5:0.5),
 F= Mobile phase (petroleum ether: hexane: chloroform : methanol ; 6:2:2:3)
 G= Mobile phase (petroleum ether : hexane : chloroform : methanol;
 14:4:12:9)
 H= Mobile phase (petroleum ether: hexane: chloroform : methanol ;
 13:3:14:10)

APPENDIX C

The results of qualitative analysis of *Mentha A.*, *Laurus N.*, *Bacopa M.* and *Hibiscus R.* oils using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy as explained in the research papers have been illustrated in this Appendix.

FT-IR ANALYSIS OF *MENTHA A.* OIL

The FT-IR spectrum exhibits the characteristic finger print band features. The very strong absorption bands at 2953.9, 1384.5 and 1291 cm^{-1} are representative for C-H, O-H and C-O stretching vibrations, characteristic of the presence of Primary alcohols. In all locations, it is noticed that the bands at 2953, 1702 and 1455 cm^{-1} are due to the stretching vibration of $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ groups and aliphatic groups. The 2723, 1669 and 1291 cm^{-1} bands are due to stretching vibration of C-H indicating aldehyde group compounds. The results are shown in the figure given below. The analysis is done with the extracts obtained from the *Mentha* species grown over different seasons. ^[45]

From this analysis, it was concluded that only some changes have occurred in chemical constituents of essential oil obtained from *Mentha arvensis*. The plant is exposed to the pollution of vehicles all the time, only minor changes in its constituents are noticed which suggests that this plant has a protective mechanism but it's not totally safe to consume, because the oil is widely used at very large scale in food industries. ^[45]

M. arvensis (site 1) university (summer season)

Figure C.1: FT-IR analysis of *Mentha A.* extract obtained in summer season

M. arvensis (site 1) university (rainy season)

M. arvensis (site2) Hazratganj (rainy season)

Figure C.2: FT-IR analysis of *Mentha A.* extract obtained in rainy season

FT-IR ANALYSIS OF *BACOPA M.* OIL

To remove any free biomass residue or compound that is not the capping ligand of the copper nanoparticles, the residual solutions of 100 ml were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min and the resulting suspensions were re-dispersed in 20 ml sterile distilled water. The whole process was repeated three times. Thereafter, the purified suspension was freeze dried to obtain dried powder. Finally, the dried copper nanoparticles were analyzed by FTIR. ^[52]

Figure C.3 shows the FT-IR spectrum obtained from *Bacopa monnieri*, leaf extract and copper nano-particles solution displays a number of absorption peaks, reflecting its complex nature and shows the multiple bands at 3320, 3301, 2180, 1637, 1372, 1022 cm^{-1} , which clearly demonstrates the N-H stretch of amide group at band 3301 cm^{-1} and 3320 cm^{-1} , and the C \equiv C stretch of alkynes at band 2180 cm^{-1} , and C-H stretch of primary alcohols and aromatic groups at band 1637 cm^{-1} and 1599 cm^{-1} . ^[52]

Figure C.3: FT-IR analysis of *Bacopa M.* extract

FT-IR ANALYSIS OF *LAURUS N.* OIL

The extract obtained from the *Laurus nobilis* was subjected to FT-IR analysis and the results are illustrated below.

The IR spectrum of the oil is provided in Figure C.4. The O–H stretching vibrations between 3200 and 3400 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of phenols and alcohols. The C–H stretching vibrations between 2800 and 3000 cm^{-1} and C–H deformation vibrations between 1350 and 1475 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of alkanes. The C=O stretching vibrations with absorbance between 1650 and 1750 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of ketones and aldehydes. The absorbance peaks between 1575 and 1675 cm^{-1} represent C=C stretching vibrations indicative of alkenes and aromatics. [57]

Figure C.4: FT-IR analysis of *Laurus nobilis* extract

FT-IR ANALYSIS OF *HIBISCUS R.* OIL

FTIR Analysis of hibiscus extract was done and the results are shown in the figure below, the spectral peak for hibiscus was shown at 1436.39 cm^{-1} for lipid origin, 1314.13 cm^{-1} for glycogen and 3429 cm^{-1} for phenolic compounds.

Fig. 1 a, FTIR spectra of powdered flower petals of hibiscus; b, FTIR spectra of powdered flower petals of Cassia.

Figure C.5: FT-IR analysis of Hibiscus oil

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